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Deliverable 6.1 Pre-operational status ecosystem fluxes

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Executive Summary

This study investigates the role of soil gas fluxes, particularly soil respiration and field capacity, as indicators of the health and sustainability of agroecosystems. These proxies are crucial for understanding soil biological activity and water dynamics, which directly affect soil health, crop productivity, and resilience in agricultural systems. A total of 258 soil samples were analyzed from orchards in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Italy, and Morocco, representing three management types: Traditional (TD), High Density (HD), and Organic (ORG). The analysis of soil respiration was conducted using the MicroResp™ technique, which measures CO₂ production as an indicator of microbial activity in response to various substrates. Field capacity was estimated using pedotransfer functions based on soil texture and organic matter content.

The results revealed significant differences in soil respiration across countries, with soils from Greece exhibiting the highest respiration rates and those from Spain showing the lowest. pH levels were found to be a key explanatory factor, with more alkaline soils displaying lower respiration rates. When examining agricultural management types, organic management showed higher soil respiration, particularly in glucose and N-acetylglucosamine (NAGA) substrates, compared to conventional management, which exhibited lower respiration rates. However, no significant differences in field capacity were found between the management types, suggesting that factors beyond management practices are more influential on field capacity. Regarding field capacity and soil compaction, intensified farming systems displayed increased soil compaction, which negatively impacted field capacity. A strong negative relationship between bulk density and field capacity was observed, indicating that management practices could influence soil compaction and water retention.

1. Introduction.

Understanding soil gas fluxes through proxies like soil respiration and field capacity is key to evaluating the health and sustainability of agroecosystems. Soil respiration reflects biological activity and serves as an indicator of CO₂ emissions, while field capacity indicates water retention and flow. These proxies help assess water dynamics and biological function, both critical for soil health, crop productivity and resilience in agricultural systems.

2. Methods and Materials.

2.1. Sample collection.

A total of 258 samples have been analysed. The sampled orchards correspond with different types of crops: Traditional (TD), High Density (HD) and Organic (ORG), from the following countries: Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy and Greece.

- Spain - 80 from 16 orchards.
- Greece - 75 from 15 orchards.
- Portugal - 25 from 5 orchards.
- Italy - 40 from 8 orchards.
- Morocco – 35 from 7 orchards.

Soil samples were collected in late spring 2023. Five samples were taken from each plot at a single depth of 0–20 cm. These samples were collected at the same LUCAS point used for the other soil analyses. They were transported in coolers to the University of Jaen laboratory. Upon arrival, the samples were air-dried for two weeks, sieved using a 2 mm mesh, and stored at 4°C until analysis.

2.2. Soil respiration analyses.

Microbial activity in the soil was evaluated using the MicroResp™ technique, which measures CO₂ production as an indicator of metabolic activity in response to different substrates. An equivalent of 0.3 g of dry soil was placed into wells of a microplate and incubated with a CO₂ detection gel sensitive to pH changes. The following substrates were used: water (control for basal respiration), glucose (readily available carbon source), lignin (recalcitrant compound indicating the capacity to degrade complex organic matter), and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine (NAGA) (a chitin-derived monomer linked to microbial activity on nitrogen-containing organic compounds). Incubation was carried out at 25°C for 6 hours, and colour changes in the detection gel were measured spectrophotometrically at 570 nm.

2.3. Field capacity.

Field capacity (FC) was estimated using the pedotransfer functions developed by Saxton and Rawls (2006), based on soil texture and organic matter content. The model uses empirical equations to predict FC from percentages of sand, silt, clay, and organic matter, assuming a standard bulk density. These calculations were performed using the following input data: soil texture (determined by hydrometer method) and organic matter (determined by loss on ignition). The estimated FC values correspond to the water content at -33 kPa of matric potential.

3. Results.

3.1. Soil respiration.

Fig 1. On the left, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of Substrate-Induced Respiration (SIR). On the right, the relative contribution of different substrates to each dimension.

In the results of this PCA (Fig 1.), we identified two principal components. The first component (which explains 56.8% of the variance) represents a grouping of respiration based on glucose and NAGA substrates, as well as basal respiration, all

positively. On the other hand, the second component (which explains 21.7% of the variance) is primarily associated negatively with respiration using the lignin substrate.

Fig 2. In blue (top), the linear model estimates and their significance levels. In orange (bottom), the ANOVA results based on the sum of squares and their significance. Significance levels are indicated as follows: * <math>p < 0.05</math>, ** <math>p < 0.01</math>.

A linear model (lm) was conducted using Dimension 1 and Dimension 2 as response variables, with soil texture components and pH as predictors (Fig. 2). Among these, pH emerged as the key explanatory factor. For Dimension 1—which is associated with basal respiration and substrate-induced respiration using glucose and N-acetylglucosamine (NAGA)—a negative relationship with pH was observed. Since the analysed soils are predominantly alkaline, this suggests that highly alkaline soils exhibit lower respiration rates. On the other hand, Dimension 2—negatively associated with lignin—showed a positive relationship with pH, which aligns with the previous interpretation and supports the observed trend.

Fig 3. PCA representation differentiated by countries.

Concerning the differentiation by countries (Fig. 3), significant differences were found in both dimension 1 and dimension 2. For dimension 1, the marginal means (emmeans) show higher respiration in the orchards of Greece and the lowest in Spain. In dimension 2, lower respiration

levels were found in Spain and Greece, while the highest levels were observed in Morocco and Portugal.

On the other hand, the relationship between country and pH was assessed using an analysis of variance (ANOVA), which revealed a statistically significant effect ($p < 0.05$). This result indicates that pH levels and, ultimately, soil type differ meaningfully across countries, and therefore, referring to country is statistically comparable to referring to pH, as the country variable significantly explains variation in soil type and pH.

This explains why the differences observed across countries show the variations in the predominant soil types characteristic of each country.

Fig 4. PCA representation differentiated by agricultural management.

Regarding the differentiation by management (Fig. 4), no clear relationship was found between management and the predominant soil type and pH, likely due to the presence of multiple countries within each management group. Therefore, the observed variation in soil respiration can be more directly attributed to the effect of management practices themselves.

In these results no significant variations were found in either dimension 1 or 2, largely due to the high variability within the groups. However, the marginal means (emmeans) show trends related to conventional management, where the values are lower than in the other treatments, indicating lower respiration across the glucose and NAGA substrate group, as well as basal respiration. In dimension 2 (lignin substrate), the trend shows that organic management has the highest value, indicating a lower respiration rate for that substrate.

Fig 5. Estimated marginal means of basal respiration across management types.

Only the management factor was found to have a direct and significant effect on basal respiration, with the model being controlled for country as a random factor. Post-hoc Tukey tests revealed higher respiration rates in the organic treatment, with the most notable difference observed in the conventional management, which resulted in the lowest respiration rates (Fig. 5).

3.2. Field capacity.

Fig 6. Boxplot graph of soil field capacity (%) grouped by country.

As observed with soil respiration, the variations displayed in Figure 6 are a result of differences in soil types—specifically, soil texture in this case, where clay soils exhibit a higher field capacity compared to sandy soils. Although the linear models account for the country effect—largely dependent on soil type—management does not show a significant effect on field capacity.

Fig 7. Boxplot graph of soil field capacity (%) grouped by management.

Fig 8. Boxplot graph of bulk density grouped by management.

Fig 9. Relationship between bulk density and field capacity.

Despite not finding significant differences in field capacity between management types (Fig. 7), we observed a pattern of increased soil compaction (as measured by bulk density) in intensified farms (Fig. 8). Similarly, we found a strong negative relationship between bulk density and field capacity (Fig. 9), suggesting that management practices could impact field capacity and water storage through compaction.

A mediation analysis was conducted to evaluate whether the effect of management field capacity was mediated by bulk density. Although a marginally significant trend was observed for a negative indirect effect of management through bulk density (ACME = -2.99, $p = 0.088$), neither the direct effect (ADE = 3.00, $p = 0.136$) nor the total effect (0.009, $p = 0.956$) were statistically significant. Therefore, there would be a (marginally significant) reduction in field capacity in intensified orchards due to the soil compaction.

4. Conclusions.

The conclusions of the study highlight the importance of soil gas fluxes as key indicators for evaluating the health and sustainability of agroecosystems, particularly through proxies such as soil respiration and field capacity. The results show that soil respiration, as a reflection of microbial activity, varied according to soil type and agricultural management conditions. It was observed that more alkaline soils exhibited lower respiration rates, suggesting that soil pH significantly influences biological activity. Additionally, geographical differences among countries showed variations in respiration, attributed to the different predominant soil types in each region. Regarding agricultural management, organic management soils showed higher respiration activity, particularly when compared to conventional management soils, which exhibited lower rates. However, no significant differences were found in field capacity between management types, although patterns of higher soil compaction were identified in intensified farms, negatively affecting field capacity. The relationship between soil bulk density and field capacity highlights the importance of considering compaction in agricultural management. In conclusion, the variability in soil gas fluxes and field capacity based on soil type, management practices, and geographical conditions underscores the need for more precise management of agroecosystems to improve soil health and agricultural sustainability.